

PATHOGENICITY CHARACTERISTICS OF CLINICAL STRAINS BELONGING TO THE GENUS ASPERGILLUS**Aliyev İ.A.,***higher education, PhD in biology, leading researcher
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Azerbaijan State Pedagogical College of MSERA***Abstract**

The presented work is devoted to the study of the characteristic features of the clinical strains of the genus *Aspergillus*. It was found that *A. fumigatus* mushroom is one of the most active representatives of conventional pathogens spreading in healthcare facilities. At the same time, it was determined that clinical strains of this fungus are the pathological agents of both allergic and invasive forms of aspergillosis.

Keywords: health facility, clinical strain, conditional pathogen, aspergillosis, pathological agent.

The increasing dynamics of mycotic diseases caused by conditionally pathogenic micromycetes has already been confirmed in world practice. It should be noted that the use of antibacterial and antifungal drugs during the treatment of people in various healthcare facilities, the use of a wide range of cytostatic and steroid hormones, the rescue of patients from the clutches of death by special surgical neonatological and resuscitation methods, on the one hand serve to bring people back to life, on the other on the other hand, it leads to zero or loss of their immunity. The skin, mucous membrane, and operated internal organs of such patients are easily infected with aspergillosis, candidiasis, etc. mycoses, which, as a secondary pathology, aggravates the general condition of the patient [5; 7; 8]. If it is taken into account that a large number of people lose their health in the construction and construction works, which are widespread in our republic, as well as almost every day, as a result of traffic accidents, and their treatment and rehabilitation are carried out using the same methods and in the same place, then. It becomes clear how complex the pathological condition is. At the same time, improper living conditions in modern megacities create the basis for people to be infected with mycotic diseases [1; 2; 3].

The purpose of the work was the study of clinical fungi, including various strains belonging to the genus *Aspergillus*, which become a potential source of infection in patients receiving treatment in various healthcare facilities.

Clinical strains belonging to the genus *Aspergillus* were obtained from the surgical, gynecological, dental and X-ray rooms, wards and dressing rooms of the central health facilities of our republic. The collected samples were cultured and identified using available markers [4; 6; 9].

As a result of the conducted research, it was determined that clinical fungal strains are widespread in the air space of operating rooms. In particular, the number of spores per unit volume of fungi belonging to the genus *Aspergillus* is expressed by higher quantitative indicators compared to others. At the same time, the number of spores of clinical strains belonging

to the genus of fungi is significantly higher on the internal organs separated from the human body by special surgical methods. This characterizes Aspergillosis as a secondary pathology as a potential source of infection. Comparative mycological analyzes prove that clinical strains of *Aspergillus fumigatus* are involved in the etiology of Aspergillosis in healthcare facilities as the most active pathological agent. It is known that Aspergillosis is an infectious-allergic disease caused by fungi belonging to the genus *Aspergillus*, including *A.fumigatus*, *A.flavus*, *A.nidulans*, *A.niger*, *A.terreus*, *A.clavatus*, *A.amstelodami*, etc is committed. By the way, it should be noted that clinical studies prove that *A.fumigatus* fungus is the pathological agent of both allergic and invasive forms of aspergillosis. At the same time, if we take into account that this fungus is conditionally pathogenic, the type of secondary pathology that will be caused depends on the immune level of the body. A comparative study of the pathogenicity characteristics of fungi belonging to the *Aspergillus* genus shows that in all cases, spores of the *A. fumigatus* fungus are noted as the primary cause of aspergillosis as a secondary pathology in patients. In other words, the air space density of spores belonging to the *A. fumigatus* fungus in operating rooms increases extremely and the virulence ability increases.

The conducted mycological examinations show that the clinical strains of *A.fumigatus* fungus, which are dislocated on the internal organs, which gradually lose their viability, increase their biological activity even more. If we take into account that the chemical composition of the internal organs is composed mainly of substances of protein origin, then there is no doubt that the *A. fumigatus* fungus synthesizes proteolytic enzymes. Studies conducted on 27 clinical strains of *A. fumigatus* prove that these fungi invade muscle tissue without any difficulty. Because the proteases secreted by the clinical strains more easily destroy the protein compounds that form the basis of the cell membrane, creating favorable conditions for the unhindered entry

of fungal hyphae into "in vivo". This plays an extremely important role in the pathogenetic activity of clinical strains of *A. fumigatus* (table 1).

However, since clinical strains that synthesize proteolytic enzymes poorly cannot invade tissues and cells, their level of virulence is extremely low. Thus, the conducted studies show that there are

Table 1.

Physiological and biochemical characteristics of different strains of *Aspergillus fumigatus* isolated from operating rooms.

№	Types of fungi	Proteolytic activity	Growth process at 37 °C	Fungi species status
1	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> (1)	+	+	K
2	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (2)	+	+	K
3	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (3)	+	+	K
4	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (4)	+	+	K
5	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (5)	+	+	K
6	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (6)	+	+	K
7	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (7)	+	+	K
8	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (8)	-	+	S
9	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (9)	-	+	S
10	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (10)	+	+	K
11	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (11)	+	+	K
12	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (12)	+	+	K
13	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (13)	-	+	S
14	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (14)	-	+	S
15	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (15)	-	+	S
16	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (16)	+	+	K
17	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (17)	+	+	K
18	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (18)	-	+	S
19	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (19)	+	+	K
20	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (20)	+	+	K
21	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (21)	+	+	K
22	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (22)	-	+	S
23	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (23)	-	+	S
24	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (24)	+	+	K
25	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (25)	+	+	K
26	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (26)	+	+	K
27	<i>A.fumigatus</i> (27)	+	+	K

correlative relationships between the enzymatic activity (proteases) of the clinical strains of the *A. fumigatus* fungus and their ability to invade the substrate. In other words, the proteolytic activity of the fungus is the main argument determining its pathogenicity.

The conducted mycological examinations show that the clinical strains of *A.fumigatus* fungus, which are dislocated on the internal organs, which gradually lose their viability, increase their biological activity even more.

The researches conducted that the clinical strains of this fungi manifest in the organism as secondary pathology with clinical symptoms. In our opinion the cultural-morphological, biochemical and molecular-genetic changes that occur in the fungal cell depending on the composition of the food environment and environmental parameters are the clinical forms of the genus *Aspergillus*.

References

1. Aliyev I.A., Agayeva N.A., Ganbarov Kh.G. The influence of temperature to the growth of opportunistic fungi of Baku city environment // International Journal of Applied and Pure Science and Agriculture. 2016, vol.2, Issue 6, p:148

2. Aliyev I.A., Muradov P.Z., Shamilov E.N. Pathogenicity and taxonomic structure of nosocomial mycobiota at the medical institutions // International Journal of Pharmaceutical Science and Healthy Care, India, Journal issue 6, vol.1, 2016,pp

3. Alker A., Smith G.W., Kim K. Characterization of *Aspergillus sydowii* (Thom et Church), a fungal pathogen of Caribbean sea fan corals. //Hydrobiologia. 2001, vol.460, №1-3, p 97-104.

4. De Hoog G.S., Guarro Y., Gene J, Fugueras M. Atlas of clinical fungi. Urtecht (Spain: CBS) ,“Universitat aaaRovirai Reus”, 2000, 1126p

5. Dagenais T.R., Keller N.P. Pathogenesis of *Aspergillus fumigatus* in invasive aspergillosis. // Clinical microbiology reviews.2009, vol.22, №3, pp:447-465.

6. Klich M.A., Pitt J.I. A laboratory guide to common *Aspergillus* species and their teleomorphs. // Common wealth scientific and industrial research organization division of food processing.// North Ryde. N.S.W.: 1992, 166 pp.

7. Latge G.P. *Aspergillus fumigatus* and aspergillosis //Clinical Micro- biology. Reviews. 1999, vol. 12. № 2, p.: 310-350.

8. Menzies D., Holmes I., Mecumesny G., Prys-Picard C., Niven R. Aspergillus sensitization is associated with airflow limitation and bronchiectasis in severe asthma: aspergillus, bronchiectasis and severe asthma // Allergy, 2011, vol.66, №5, pp:679-685.

9. Sabino R, Burco J., Valente J., Verissimo C., Clemons K., Stevens D., Tell I. Molecular identification of clinical and environmental avian Aspergillus isolates // Archive Microbiology, 2019, vol.201, №2, pp:253-257.